

with increase in temperature showing that the complexation reaction is exothermic; whereas in the case of Th^{4+} complexes, the $\log K_{\text{stab}}$ values increase with temperature indicating an endothermic process. These observations are confirmed by -ve value of ΔH in the case of UO_2^{2+} complex and positive ΔH in the case of Th^{4+} complexes. This explains the variation of stability constants with temperature for the two metal ions in opposite direction (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log \beta$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ AND $\text{Th}(\text{IV})$ COMPLEXES OF DL-NOR-LEUCINE AT $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4)

Constants* and thermodynamic functions	$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ complexes			$\text{Th}(\text{IV})$ complexes		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
$\log K_1$	7.81	7.72	7.61	—	—	—
$\log K_2$	6.92	6.72	6.62	8.52	8.57	8.62
$\log K_3$				8.20	8.23	8.27
$\log K_4$				4.99	5.49	5.99
ΔG (Kcal/mole)		-20.02			-30.90	
ΔH (Kcal/mole)		-10.38			24.48	
ΔS (cal/deg/mole)		31.81			182.77	

* Uncertainty limit ± 0.02

The negative values of ΔG in both cases indicate that the reaction proceeds spontaneously.

The positive ΔS values (Table 1) obtained indicate that entropy factor strongly favours the chelate formation, and stabilises the complex due to the liberation of water molecules from the ion accompanying complexation.

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Stability and Thermodynamic Constants of Some Alkaline Earth Salts of Adrenalin Ion

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ADRENALINE (epinephrine) is 1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl amino ethanol and is used as a vasoconstrictor. With the belief that metal complexes play an important part in the biological activity of drugs¹, as most of the drugs possess chelating structures initially or after metabolic alterations, much work has been done to study the avidity of various drugs for metals. Study of chelation of catechol amines with some transition metals has been reported earlier²⁻⁵. But no information is available on chelation of M^{2+} ions with adrenaline. In this communication we report the results of our studies on M^{2+} -adrenaline complexes, where $\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Be}^{2+}$, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high purity analytical grade. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion and the ligand solutions and the experimental details are the same as reported earlier⁶.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by conductometric titrations. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique⁶ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was followed to determine various formation constants at three temperatures, 0, 25 and 37° and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl. The experimental procedure consists in titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solutions with a 0.2 M alkali solution.

- 5 ml of 0.02 M HCl solution,
- Solution (i) + 10 ml of 0.01 M adrenaline solution,
- Mixture (ii) + 5 ml of 0.002 M metal ion solution.

The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M KCl solution, keeping the total volume at 50 ml with double distilled water.

The values of $\bar{n}H$, \bar{n} and pL^- were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti equations⁷, and the values

of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were recorded directly from the formation curves (Fig. 1). The refined values for the same were computed by the method of least squares and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY AND THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS OF M^{2+} -ADRENALINE CHELATES

Temp. °C	H^+	$\mu=0.1 M (KCl)$					
		Be(II)	Mg(II)	Ca(II)	Sr(II)	Ba(II)	
$\log K_1$	0	9.57	9.50	6.50	5.96	5.25	4.72
	25	8.95	8.63	6.00	5.45	4.71	4.02
	37	AD 8.45	8.19	5.69	5.11	4.40	3.22
		NAD*8.30	7.25	5.16	4.74	4.30	3.45
$\log K_2$	0		4.41	2.03	2.03	1.70	1.11
	25		3.98	2.19	1.33	1.14	1.89
	37		3.01	1.85	1.30	1.02	1.05
$\log \beta_2$	0		13.91	8.88	7.99	6.95	5.88
	25		12.61	8.19	6.78	5.85	5.91
	37		11.20	7.54	6.41	5.42	4.27
ΔG_1	25		-11.81	-6.94	-6.18	-5.52	-4.80
ΔG_2	25		-6.80	-3.77	-3.16	-2.64	-1.99
ΔG_n	25		-17.16	-9.88	-8.79	-7.00	-5.98
ΔH_1	25		-10.72	-9.68	-8.19	-6.55	-8.93
ΔH_2	25		-9.97	-4.32	-6.55	-5.33	-2.98
ΔH_n	25		-21.71	-16.38	-17.27	-22.33	-16.97
ΔS_1	25		1.99	-9.14	-6.74	-3.46	-13.85
ΔS_2	25		-10.67	-1.82	-11.38	-9.03	-3.31
ΔS_n	25		-15.27	-21.78	-28.47	-51.44	-36.86

ΔG_n and ΔH_n in Kcal mol⁻¹ and ΔS_n in cal deg⁻¹ mol⁻¹

AD=Adrenaline; NAD=Noradrenaline

*Values from Ref. 10.

The stepwise and overall thermodynamic parameters computed for the complexation reactions studied were ΔG , ΔH and ΔS utilising the Vant-Hoff's isotherm, the isobar and the Gibbs-Helmholtz equations, respectively under the experimental conditions (Table 1).

Isolation and determination of structures of the isolated complexes was done as described earlier for the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes⁴.

Result and Discussion

The stoichiometric studies based on conductometric studies utilising conductometric titrations indicated formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes between M^{2+} and adrenaline. This found further confirmation in the maximum values of \bar{n} obtained for the systems studied (which were in no case found greater than 1.80) (Fig. 1).

An analysis of the formation curves (Fig. 1) indicated that adrenaline follows the same sequence of addition to the metal ions as has been reported for the amino acids⁵, that is, one atom of the metal first combined with one molecule of adrenaline. The 1 : 1 complex thus formed did not appreciably combine with a second molecule of adrenaline to give the 1 : 2 complex, until at least 75% of the 1 : 1 complex had been formed. This indicated that the formation of the two species is independent of each other.

The values of formation constants and free energy change (Table 1) give the normal order of stability⁶ for these complexes i.e. Be > Mg > Ca >

Fig. 1. Formation curves M^{2+} -adrenaline complexes, 25°, 1 Ba, 2 Mg, 3 Ca, 4 Sr and 5 Ba.

Sr > Ba. This is the same as reported for noradrenaline complexes¹⁰. However, compared to noradrenaline complexes, adrenaline adducts are found more stable in accordance with their pK_a values, and may be accounted for in the light of the fact that in the secondary amino group of adrenaline molecule, the presence of CH_3 group in place of the hydrogen (of primary amino group in noradrenaline) has base strengthening effect.

The analytical data (Table 2) gave the composition of the complexes isolated to be $ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O$,

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF M^{2+} -ADRENALINE CHELATES

	Metal	% Nitrogen	H_2O
Be($C_9H_{11}O_2N$) ₂	2.38 (2.41)	7.49 (7.50)	—
Mg($C_9H_{11}O_2H$) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	5.59 (5.66)	6.59 (6.60)	8.45 (8.49)
Ca($C_9H_{11}O_2N$) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	9.00 (9.09)	6.30 (6.36)	8.10 (8.17)

All the chelates are soluble in water and alcohol, hydroscopic in nature and decompose before melting.

Values in parenthesis are the calculated values.

where $M=M^{2+}$ and L =the monovalent negative ion of the ligand. The important frequencies in the ir spectra of the isolated complexes indicate that the chelation has taken place through the phenolic hydroxyl group forming a five membered ring as reported earlier¹⁰.

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Evaluation of "Effective Ionic Diameter" 'A' from Hydration Number 'h' of a Strong Electrolyte Solution

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It has been shown in a previous publication¹ that above 0.1 M, variation with concentration of the mean molal activity coefficient γ of the ions of a strong 1 : 1 electrolyte solution can be represented by the following equation,

$$\log \gamma = -\frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} + \log \frac{C}{m d_0} + \frac{0.018 m r (r + h - \nu)}{2.3 \nu (1 + 0.018 m r)} + \frac{h - \nu}{\nu} \log (1 + 0.018 m r) - \frac{h}{\nu} \log (1 - 0.018 m h) \quad (1)$$

where B is a constant which can be calculated from theory, A the effective ionic diameter, C the molar and m the molal concentration respectively, d_0 the density of the solvent, r the volume fraction, h the hydration number and ν the number of ions formed by a molecule of the electrolyte.

It may be mentioned that according to Glueckauf² and Robinson and Stokes³, $\log \gamma$ may be expressed as follows :

$$\log \gamma = \log \gamma^{el} + \log \gamma^{vis} \quad \dots (2)$$

In equation (1) $-\frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} + \log \frac{C}{m d_0}$ represent

$\log \gamma^{el}$ as deduced by the author¹ and the rest represent $\log \gamma^{vis}$ as deduced by Glueckauf².

For each electrolyte the values of the two empirical constants A and h are to be found from experimental data on the activity coefficient of the ions. The two constants will, however, be reduced effectively to one if a quantitative relation can be found between them.

It may be mentioned that A can also be found from data on equivalent conductivity λ of a strong 1 : 1 electrolyte solution using the following equation deduced by the author⁴.

$$\lambda = \lambda_g - \frac{mG}{\sqrt{A}} C^{1/2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where λ_g represents equivalent conductance at infinite dilution and m and G are constants which can be calculated from theory.

In a paper⁵ already published A has been defined by the following expression :

$$A = (r_- + r_+ + H) \quad \dots (4)$$

where r_- and r_+ represent the Pauling radii of the negative and positive ions and H the contribution of hydration of the ions to A, all expressed in Angström unit.

For the chlorides of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Cs^+ and H^+ the following relation has now been found to exist between H and h.

$$\frac{4}{3} \pi H^3 = (h - r) \frac{18}{N} \text{cc} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{or } H = \left[(h - r) \frac{30}{4.19} \right]^{1/3} \text{Å} \quad \dots (5a)$$

In equation (5), 18 is the molar volume of water at 25°, N the Avogadro number and $r = \phi_v / V_w$ where ϕ_v is the apparent molal volume of the electrolyte at concentration 1 N and V_w is the volume of one gram molecule of water ; thus r represents Glueckauf's volume fraction.

In Table 1 are recorded the data on the electrolytes mentioned above. In column 1 of the table under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the electrolyte and the values of the corresponding r. In the columns 6 and 7 of the table are recorded the values of A in Angström found from measurements of activity coefficient¹ and conductance of the ions of the electrolyte⁶ in the concentration ranges 0.001 M to 4.0 M and 0.001 M to 0.1 M, respectively.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF OBSERVED AND CALCULATED VALUES OF A AT 25°

Miscellaneous	$r_- + r_+$	h	Calculated H	Calculated A	Observed A from Acti- vity	Conduc- tance
LiCl r=1.03	2.41	5.60	3.20	5.61	5.62	
NaCl r=1.03	2.76	4.06	2.79	5.55	5.52	5.52
KCl r=1.4	3.14	3.0	2.26	5.40	5.52	5.48
CsCl r=2.3	3.50	2.40	0.89	4.39	4.33	
HCl r=1.05	3.89	5.34	3.11	7.0	6.92	5.59

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the calculated values of A agree well with those found from measurements of mean molal activity coefficient of the ions. They also agree well with the values of A found from conductivity measurement except in the case of HCl. It may be attributed in the latter case to the peculiar mechanism of conduction of current by the H^+ ion which is assumed to gain by the diameter of the oxygen atom (1.48 Å) in the process. If 1.48 is added to 5.59, we get 7.07 Å which is very close to the calculated value of A of HCl.